

Modification of Fermi-Dirac/Bose-Einstein Distributions Based on Pure State Entropy?

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In a previous note (1) we argued that for a wavefunction $W(x,t) = \sum_n a_n \exp(iE_n t)$ $W_n(x)$, the entropy for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls from (2) is:

$S/(-k) = \sum_n |a_n|^2 \ln |a_n|^2$ ((1)) and should be modified to: $S/(-k) = \sum_n |a_n|^2 \ln |a_n|^2 + \sum_n |a_n|^2 S_p(n,L) + \sum_n |a_n|^2 S_x(L)$ ((2)) where S_p and S_x are the pure state momentum and spatial entropies i.e. $S_p/(-k) = \int dp |a_n(p)|^2 \ln |a_n(p)|^2$ and $S_x/(-k) = \int dx |W_n(x)|^2 \ln |W_n(x)|^2$.

In (2) the Clausius relationship: $dQ/T = dS$ is used where $dQ = \sum_n E_n d|a_n|^2$ and T is temperature to find an expression for $|a_n|^2$. In general this would be: $|a_n|^2 = \exp(-E_n/T)$, but with ((2)) we find: $|a_n|^2 = \exp(-E_n/kT) \exp(-1-B(n))$ ((3)) where $B(n) = S_p(n) + S_x(L)$. L portions from S_p and S_x cancel so there is no L dependence, L being the size of the box.

Given the different form ((3)) we suggest that the Fermi-Dirac (FD) and Bose-Einstein (BE) distributions may change if one uses the grand partition function approach. For example, $\exp(-n_i \epsilon_i/kT)$ is replaced by: $\exp(-n_i \epsilon_i/kT) \exp(-n_i(1+B(n)))$. This leads to changes in the FD and BE distributions: $z \exp(-E_i/kT) \exp(-1-B(i)) / [1 \pm \exp(-u/kT) \exp(-E_i/kT) \exp(-1-B(i))]$ where $z = \exp(u/kT)$, u being the chemical potential. In the high n limit $B(n) \rightarrow \text{constant}$ (3) so the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution remains unchanged. The MB distribution has been verified to high precision and so modifications related to $1+B(n)$ might have been noticed had $B(n)$ remained a function of n .

Pure State Entropy for a Particle in a Box with Infinite Walls

The pure state entropies are usually given separately as spatial entropy S_x and momentum entropy S_p . S_x depends on $\ln(L)$ and S_p on $-\ln(L)$ so if one adds the two, L dependence disappears. This we argue is important if one wishes to have a quantum adiabatic transformation (L change) be linked with no change in entropy as in (2). From (3) one has:

$$S_x = \ln(2L/x_0) \quad ((3a)) \text{ and}$$

$$S_p \rightarrow \text{infinite} \quad \ln[4 \cdot 3.14 \cdot \hbar \exp(2(1-g))/L p_0] \quad ((3b)) \quad ((4)) \text{ where } g \text{ is the Euler constant}$$

The L dependence of ((3b)) is the same for any n and $p_0 = \hbar$. Thus:

$S_p + S_x = B(n)$ with no L dependence. A closed form for S_p is not easy to obtain, but it may be computed numerically.

Entropy for a Particle in a Box

Consider the wavefunction:

$$W(x,t) = \sum_n a_n \exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x) \quad ((4))$$

In (2) the corresponding Shannon's entropy is given as:

$$S/(-k) = \sum_n |a_n| \ln|a_n| \quad ((5))$$

In (1), however, we suggested using $P(x)P(p) |a_n|$ as the Shannon's probability leading to:

$$S/(-k) = |a_n| \ln|a_n| + |a_n| S_p + |a_n| S_x = |a_n| \ln|a_n| + |a_n| (S_p + S_x)$$

$$\text{With } S_p + S_x = B(n) \quad ((6))$$

|a_n| as a Function of T

In (2) dQ/T is set equal to dS where:

$dQ = \sum_n E_n d|a_n|$ ((7)) and T is temperature. Using ((6)) and considering $d|a_n|$'s to be independent, one has:

$$|a_n| = \exp(-E_n/kT) \exp(-1-B(n)) \quad ((7))$$

We suggest this should be used in the grand partition function in place of $\exp(-E_n/kT)$.

Grand Partition Function Results

From (4) the grand partition function is (with $z = \exp(u/kT)$, u being the chemical potential)

$$Q_{\text{grand}}(z, V, T) = \sum_N \sum_{\{n_i\}} \text{(where } \sum_i n_i = N) z^{\sum_i n_i} \exp(-E_i/T)^{n_i} \exp(-1-B(i))^{n_i} \quad ((8))$$

For a fermion $n_i = 0$ or 1 while for a boson it takes on all integer values. ((8)) seems to imply that regular results for the FD and BE distributions hold, but with $\exp(-E_i/kT)$ replaced with $\exp(-E_i/kT) \exp(-1-B(i))$. Thus:

$$\langle n_i \rangle_{\text{FD}} = z \exp(-E_i/kT) \exp(-1-B(i)) / \{ 1 + z \exp(-E_i/kT) \exp(-1-B(i)) \} \quad ((9a))$$

$$\langle n_i \rangle_{\text{BE}} = z \exp(-E_i/kT) \exp(-1-B(i)) / \{ 1 - z \exp(-E_i/kT) \exp(-1-B(i)) \} \quad ((9b))$$

Here i represents the i th energy level.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Result

For $i \rightarrow \text{infinite}$ $S_p(i) \rightarrow \text{constant}$ so it is independent of the energy level. Thus for $n \rightarrow \text{infinite}$:

$S_x + S_p \rightarrow \text{constant}$

To convert the FD or BE distributions into the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution one considers high energy levels i for which one should have $1 + B(i) = C_1 = \text{constant}$. Thus it seems that the MB distribution is unchanged by the factor $1 + B(i) = C_1$. This is important as the MB distribution has been measured accurately and does not seem to be modified based on energy level.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the pure state entropy for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls $S_p(n) + S_x$, where n is the energy level, affects the usual statistical factor $\exp(-E_n/kT)$. Using $dQ/T = dS$ with $dS = \sum \text{over } n \left[\frac{1}{\Omega} \ln \left(\frac{\Omega}{\Omega - 1} \right) + \frac{1}{\Omega} (S_p(n) + S_x) \right]$ together with $S_p + S_x = B(n)$ we find that $\Omega = \exp(-E_n/kT) \exp(-1 - B(n))$. Using this in the grand canonical partition function changes the FD and BE distributions by changing $\exp(-E_n/kT)$ to $\exp(-E_n/kT) \exp(-1 - B(n))$. As $n \rightarrow \text{infinite}$ i.e the MB case, $B(n) \rightarrow \text{constant}$ so the pure state entropy effect should disappear for the Maxwell-Boltzmann situation. It seems that $B(n)$ needs to be computed numerically.

References

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